

Table 1. Yield performance of Ranjini. Kerala, India.

Trial	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Ranjini	Check ^a
RRS, Moncompu (1990-92) (3 seasons)	4.5	3.1
Multilocation trials (MLT) (6 research stations, 1991)	3.2	2.7
MLT (cultivators' fields in five locations, 1992)	5.6	3.2
All India Coordinated Trials (IVT-IME, 1993)	4.5	4.0
Farm trials in five locations	4.7	3.8

^aCheck variety was Asha at RRS, MLT, and farm trials; it was Retna for IVT-IME.

Table 2. Reaction of Ranjini to pests and diseases.^a RRS, Moncompu, Kerala, India.

Variety	Gall midge	BPH	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Blast
Ranjini	1.2	1.0	1.6	2.3	0.8
MO 5 (Asha)	3.2	1.6	3.0	3.1	5.0

^a Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0-9.

Improved Sona. The breeding line KAU M 28-1-1 (IET13706) from the cross MO 5/Improved Sona performed well in yield trials and was released as Ranjini (MO 12) in 1966 for use in the three seasons of Kerala (virippu, Apr-May to Aug-Sep; mundakan, Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan; and punja, Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr). It is a short-duration (115-120 d),

dwarf (90-95 cm) variety with red-kernel medium-bold grains, and resistant to blast and brown planthopper (BPH).

In yield trials, Ranjini consistently outyielded local checks (Table 1). It also showed tolerance for gall midge, sheath blight, and sheath rot (Table 2). ■

Seed technology

On-farm seed priming to accelerate germination in rainfed, dry-seeded rice

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Demand for rice is increasing in West Africa, but farmers in upland rice areas face the twin constraints of drought and competition with weeds. Fast germination, establishment, and vigorous early growth of seedlings are essential to produce reasonable yields, particularly where presowing tillage and seedbed preparation are minimal.

Recent work at WARDA has produced interspecific hybrids by crossing *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* to give new plant types that offer high production potential allied to fast germination and enhanced weed suppression. Other work on improving the establishment of small-grained cereals, including rice in India, suggests that simple practices, such as soaking seed in water before sowing (on-farm seed priming), very effectively improve crop establishment. Combining fast-germinating varieties with on-farm seed priming should be of great benefit to rice

Time for 50% germination (h)

Effect of seed priming on germination. Numbers on columns are hours saved by priming.

farmers in marginal environments.

We tested 11 different varieties for their response to soaking in water for 24 h at 30 °C (see table). After soaking, the seeds were surface-dried with a cloth and then "sown" on moistened filter paper and kept at 30 °C. The figure compares the germination time for these primed seeds to nonprimed seeds. All lines responded positively to priming for 24 h, a limit previously determined as safe (i.e., not leading irreversibly to germination after surface drying) in Indian rice cultivars. The mean time for 50% germination of nonprimed seed was 46 h, which was reduced to 32 h by priming. The time saved by priming ranged from 7 h in CG20, an *O. glaberrima* variety, to 20 h in

Names and plant types of varieties in the figure.

Number in figure	Variety	Type
1	WAB 56-50	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
2	WAB 56-104	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
3	WABC 165	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
4	CG 14	<i>O. glaberrima</i>
5	CG 20	<i>O. glaberrima</i>
6	WAB 450-24-3-2-P18-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
7	WAB 450-1-B-P-106-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
8	WAB 450-24-2-3-P33-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
9	LAC 23	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>
10	Moroberekan	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>
11	SP 4	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>

SP4, a traditional *O. sativa* variety.

Participatory research using on-farm seed priming in India has shown that farmers prefer to soak their seeds for less than 24 h to avoid the possibility of premature germination if sowing is delayed for any reason. They report a range of benefits following overnight soaking, and our preliminary tests of germination following priming for 8 and 16 h support this conclusion. Further research is in progress to quantify the benefits of seed priming under West African conditions. ■

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